

Synthesis, spectral and pharmacological studies of some transition metal complexes derived from Schiff base of acetazolamide drug

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Abstract : Transition metal complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and VO^{IV} have been synthesized from Schiff base of acetazolamide drug, that is, 5-acetamido-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-sulphonamide. Elemental analyses suggest ML₂ stoichiometry for all metals. All the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature as suggested by conductivity data. The ligand behaves as bidentate O, N donor and forms coordinate bonds through C=N and phenolic oxygen. Magnetic susceptibility, electronic, IR, ESR and TGA spectral studies suggest that Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes possess octahedral geometry, whereas, Zn^{II} and VO^{IV} complexes exhibit tetrahedral and square pyramidal geometry respectively. The ligand and some of the synthesized complexes were screened for their antibacterial and diuretic activity also.

Keywords : Schiff base, acetazolamide, stoichiometry, non-electrolytic, antibacterial, diuretic activity.

Introduction

The co-ordination chemistry of Schiff base as bidentate ligands gained much importance because of their biological and industrial applications^{1,2}. It has been established that biological activity of Schiff base is enhanced on metal chelation^{3,4}. The study of transition metal complexes is of great interest due to their biological activities^{5,6} which are frequently higher for the metal complexes than the free Schiff base⁷. In view of the interest involved in these compounds on account of their biological uses, the acetazolamide-salicylaldehyde Schiff base (L) has been synthesized. In the present paper we are reporting the synthesis and characterization of ligand and its Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and VO^{IV} complexes. The diuretic and antibacterial activity of ligand and some complexes have also been studied.

Results and discussion

The analytical data of the complexes and their molar

Fig. 1. Structure of ligand.

conductance values are given in Table 1. All these complexes are analyzed for 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the type ML₂. On the basis of these characterizations it has been found that all the complexes are non-hygroscopic, stable at room temperature, insoluble in water but fairly soluble in DMSO. The molar conductance values of these complexes are too low to account for their electrolytic behaviour⁸.

IR spectra :

Complexes and their assignments are listed in Table 2. The IR spectra of the complexes indicate that the ligand behaves as bidentate and the metal coordinates via azomethine nitrogen and phenolic -OH groups. The shift

Table 1. Elemental analysis, color, melting points and conductance data for ligand and metal complexes

Sl. no.	Ligand/ Complexes	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					M.p. (°C)	Color	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		C	H	N	S	M			
1.	L	39.01 (40.46)	4.08 (3.06)	18.21 (17.16)	19.50 (19.61)	-	242	Pale yellow	-
2.	VOL_2	37.16 (36.82)	2.47 (2.51)	15.97 (15.62)	18.26 (17.85)	7.26 (7.10)	230	Yellow	12.5
3.	$[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	38.46 (37.13)	2.63 (2.53)	15.69 (15.75)	18.10 (18.00)	3.38 (3.52)	355	Brown	15.3
4.	$[\text{FeL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	34.79 (35.59)	2.71 (2.43)	15.02 (15.09)	16.91 (17.25)	7.81 (7.53)	360	Black	10.4
5.	$[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	35.40 (35.43)	2.45 (2.51)	15.02 (15.03)	17.24 (17.18)	7.95 (7.91)	260	Dirty green	11.8
6.	$[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	35.00 (35.45)	2.80 (2.41)	14.93 (15.03)	17.14 (17.18)	7.96 (7.88)	260	Green	13.0
7.	$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	36.98 (36.00)	2.50 (2.91)	15.69 (16.67)	17.93 (17.50)	8.86 (8.91)	199	Dark green	14.6
8.	ZnL_2	36.78 (36.90)	2.49 (2.51)	15.69 (15.65)	17.91 (17.89)	9.07 (9.14)	238	White	16.0

Table 2. Thermal decomposition of metal complexes

Sl. no.	Metal complexes	Total wt. for TGA (mg)	Temp. range of water loss (°C)	% of water loss		Decomposition temp. (°C)	% wt. of residue
				Found	Calcd.		
1.	$[\text{FeL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	9.142	~ 170–200	3.42 (4.29)		240–500	18.90 (19.05)
2.	$[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	6.883	~ 200	4.32 (4.41)		230–600	10.18 (9.19)
3.	$[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	5.660	~ 200	4.01 (4.41)		240–600	8.52 (9.17)

of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ to lower wave number by 30–40 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicates that these groups are involved in complexation⁹. The ligand shows strong band at 3410 cm^{-1} due to phenolic -OH group¹⁰. This band is absent in all the metal complexes indicating the involvement of this group in complex formation¹¹. Moreover, the shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ phenolic bands from 1280 cm^{-1} in ligand to 1280–1296 cm^{-1} in the spectra of metal complexes supports the coordination of the phenolic oxygen atom to the metal ion¹². The complexes show a broad band in the region 3410–3540 cm^{-1} suggesting the presence of co-ordinated water¹³. The bands appearing in the region 508–530 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ modes¹⁴. The bands appearing

in the region 412–468 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ modes¹⁵. In addition to these bands vanadyl complex exhibit the characteristic stretching frequency for $\text{V}=\text{O}$ ¹⁶ at 952 cm^{-1} .

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in solution state. The electronic spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complex displayed bands at 715, 585 and 460 nm assigned for ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transitions respectively¹⁷. The electronic spectra of manganese(II) complex showed four weak bands 625, 505, 483 and 374 nm which have been assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6T_{1g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ respectively¹⁸. Elec-

tronic spectra of iron(II) complex showed a weak intensity band at 924 nm which is assigned to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ transition and the second at 507 nm which may be due to charge transfer, transition¹⁹. The electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complex showed two bands at 548 nm and 444 nm assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively²⁰. This suggest an octahedral geometry for cobalt(II)²¹. The nickel(II) complex exhibited three bands at 976, 590 and 425 nm corresponding to spin allowed transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ indicating an octahedral geometry²² around the metal ion. The electronic spectra of copper(II) complex showed three bands at 479, 671 and 779 nm assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ respectively. The broadening of the band observed at 479 nm may be due to John-Teller effect²³. The zinc(II) complex is found to be diamagnetic as expected for d^{10} system and may have tetrahedral geometry²⁴.

Magnetic susceptibility data :

The magnetic moment obtained for the oxovanadium(IV) complex at room temperature is 1.77 B.M. This is due to spin only value of oxovanadium(IV) square pyramidal complex²⁵. The manganese(II) complex exhibits magnetic moment value 5.50 B.M., which is close to spin only value of 5.90 B.M. for high spin octahedral, manganese(II) complexes²⁶. The magnetic moment obtained for iron(II) complex is 5.18 B.M. which supports

its high spin octahedral configuration²⁷. The cobalt(II) complex shows magnetic moment of 4.63 B.M. suggesting an octahedral environment around the metal ion²⁸. The nickel(II) complex exhibit magnetic moment value 2.82 B.M. suggesting that it may have octahedral geometry²⁹. The copper(II) complex exhibits magnetic moment 1.74 B.M agreeable to distorted geometry of copper(II) complex³⁰.

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectra of iron(II) and copper(II) complexes were recorded in DMSO at LNT (liquid nitrogen temperature) and RT (room temperature). The spectrum of the Cu complex at RT shows one intense absorption band in the high field. At LNT Cu^{II} complex shows four well-resolved peaks with low field region. The g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} components have been calculated respectively from the low and high intensity envelopes. The values obtained for Cu^{II} complex are $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$ indicating that the Cu^{II} lies predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital³¹. The observed values of α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 of the Cu^{II} complex is less than unity that indicates that complex has some covalent character in ligand environment³². The EPR spectrum of Fe^{II} complex at both RT and LNT consists of single broad peak of high intensity explaining its paramagnetic character and it is supported by the value of magnetic moment also. The values of $g_{\parallel} = g_{\perp}$ and g_{av} less than two predicts the presence of vacant energy shells in Fe^{II} ion to accept the electron pair from ligand³³.

Fig. 2. ESR graph of Cu^{II} complex of ligand

Thermogravimetric study :

The TGA results of Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are recorded in Table 2. The results of TGA reveal that all the complexes followed the same pattern of thermal decomposition. All the complexes showed a slight depression near 170–200 °C. The weight loss at this temperature range is found to be equivalent to two water molecules for these complexes indicating them to be coordinated water³⁴. Thereafter, the complexes showed rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of the organic constituents³⁵. The decomposition continues upto ~600 °C and finally stable metal oxides are formed³⁶.

Antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activity of ligand and their metal complexes are given in Table 3. Better activities of some of the metal complexes as compared to the ligand can be explained by chelation theory. The theory explains that decrease in polarizability of the metal cloud enhance the lipophilicity of the complexes which leads to the breakdown of permeability of the cells resulting in interference with normal cell process. Antibacterial activity of the ligand and complexes reveal that the activity zone of inhibition for all the complexes against *Escherichia coli* except Cu^{II} complex is higher as compared to ligand. VO^{IV} complex

Fig. 3. TGA graph of Fe^{II} complex of ligand.

Fig. 4. TGA graph of Co^{II} complex of ligand.

of the ligand showed higher activity with 20 mm inhibition whereas the standard drug Streptomycin showed 18 mm inhibition at the same concentration.

Table 3. Antibacterial screening data of the ligand L and its complexes

Sl. no.	Ligand/ Complexes	Antibacterial activity zone of inhibition (mm)	
		<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
1.	L	9.32	11.22
2.	VOL ₂	20.28	23.44
3.	[MnL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	15.36	18.28
4.	[FeL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	11.11	12.30
5.	[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	14.36	17.38
6.	[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	11.29	6.39
7.	[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	7.02	12.32
8.	ZnL ₂	17.38	16.51
9.	Streptomycin (Standard)	18.00	16.23

Fig. 5. Antibacterial screening of VO^{IV} complex of ligand.

The antibacterial activity of all the complexes against *Bacillus subtilis* except Ni^{II} complex with 6 mm inhibition, showed higher activity with 12–23 mm inhibition. Standard drug Streptomycin showed only 16 mm inhibition at the same concentration as of the test drug. On the basis of these observations it can be said that complexation or chelation increases the antibacterial activity³⁷.

Diuretic activity :

The diuretic activity of the compounds VO^{IV} and Cu^{II} was tested in white albino mice and recorded in Table 4. All the selected test compounds, ligand and standard drug acetazolamide (AZM) at a dose of 0.24 mg suspended in 0.5% gum acacia administrated to animals of the respective group. The result revealed that metal complexes appear to have more diuretic activity as compared to the respective ligand and pure drug. Out of the selected complexes VOL₂ and CuL₂ both have significant diuretic activity as compared to ligand and parent drug but VOL₂

complex has more diuretic activity than CuL₂ complex. Thus it is revealed that complexation can increase the diuretic activity of the parent drug³⁸.

Table 4. Diuretic screening data of the pure drug, ligand and its complexes

Group	Ligand/ Complexes	Average vol. of urine (μL)			Final average (μL)
		1:00	3:00	5:00	
		pm	pm	pm	
I	Control	97.72	160.86	68.30	180.96 ± 47.293
II	AZM	113.55	184.64	109.79	135.99 ± 42.171
III	L	74.94	208.80	170.77	151.50 ± 68.978
IV	VOL ₂	306.07	314.40	355.15	355.21 ± 26.264
V	[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	215.81	236.34	225.86	226.00 ± 10.266

Fig. 6. Diuretic screening (T.S kidney) of VO^{IV} and Cu^{II} complex of ligand.

Fig. 7. M = Mn/Fe/Ni/Cu/Co

Fig. 8. (M = Zn)

Fig. 9

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR/GR grade and purchased from E. Merck (USA). Chemicals were used without any purification and acetazolamide drug was provided by Shalaks Pharmaceuticals.

Elemental analyses were carried out on model 240 Perkin elemental analyzer at CDRI, Lucknow. Metal contents were determined gravimetrically³⁹. Conductivity measurements were made in anhydrous DMF on a Systronic model 305 (India) Conductivity Bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes in the solid state were determined by vibrating sample magnetometer at Centre for Advance Technology, Indore at room temperature. The electronic spectra of the metal complexes in DMF were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer UV

WinLab spectrophotometer at School of Studies in Chemistry and Biochemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain. The infrared spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} also at School of Studies in Chemistry and Biochemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain. EPR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX-300 spectrophotometer and X-E-4 bands spectrometer at LNT (liquid nitrogen temperature) and RT (room temperature), respectively at IIT, Chennai. Thermogravimetric measurements were carried out at SICART, Gujarat in the range of 50–700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

The pharmacological activities were tested *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *In vitro* tests were conducted for growth inhibitory against *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* using Streptomycin as standard by filter paper disc method⁴⁰. The diuretic activity of the compounds (VOL_2 and CuL_2) was tested in white albino mice at Jawaharlal Nehru Cancer Hospital and Research Centre, Bhopal. Mice were fed with standard rodent pallet diet and acidified double distilled water. All the selected test compounds, ligand and standard drug acetazolamide (AZM) at a dose of 0.24 mg suspended in 0.5% gum acacia were administrated to animals of respective group. One group of animal was taken as control. For the measurement of weight of urine Whatman no.1 filter paper was used. The urine weight was recorded after two hours.

Preparation of Schiff base :

Equimolar (0.01 M) solutions of pure drug (Provided by Shalaks Pharmaceutical, Mumbai, India) and salicylaldehyde were separately dissolved in methanol-water mixture (1 : 1) and refluxed for four hours and kept for a day. Pale yellow crystals of acetazolamide Schiff base were formed in the reaction mixture which were filtered and washed thoroughly with 50% methanol-water mixture, dried over vacuum and weighed. Melting point of Schiff base was recorded.

Synthesis of complexes :

For the synthesis of complexes, 0.006 M ligand solution was prepared in 60% acetone-water solvent and refluxed for four hours with 0.003 M solution of metal salts separately. The refluxed solutions were kept for some days. Solid crystalline compounds appeared in the solu-

tion, which were filtered, washed with 60% acetone-water mixture, dried and weighed. Melting points of the complexes were recorded.

Conclusion :

Hence on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic moment data, conductivity measurements and spectral studies we propose octahedral structure for Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes, square pyramidal geometry for VO^{IV} complex and tetrahedral geometry for Zn^{II} complex.

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